

On the drivers of extremist voting: economic and cultural dimensions.

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Summary

1. We explain the electoral support for extremist parties, with a focus on nationalistic, right-wing populist parties.
2. We rely on a unique panel dataset covering 300 Flemish municipalities in Belgium, encompassing Belgian national elections between 1999 and 2019.
3. The electoral success of nationalistic, populist right-wing parties is more prevalent in cantons that do not experience economic distress but that are affected by immigration inflows.
4. Left and green parties display better electoral performances in cantons undergoing economic difficulties, while immigration inflow is not a relevant factor to attract left or green votes.
5. Right-wing, populist support seems to be partially rooted in a feeling of cultural and economic threat identified with migrants, which calls for migration policies that address this feeling of threat while considering both the economic and cultural dimensions.
6. Regarding the economic dimension, policy-makers should aim at reassuring natives about their social rights and entitlements. In relation to the cultural element, they should encourage smooth intergroups contacts to mitigate hostility towards new immigrants and to prevent the formation of prejudices about newcomers.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, political landscapes worldwide have been significantly influenced by a pervasive rise of extremist parties, often characterised by

nationalistic and/or populist traits - particularly on the right side of the political spectrum. These political developments have often entailed a polarization of the public debate, posing challenges to effective decision-making within democracies (Alesina and Tabellini, 1990;

Azzimotti, 2011). Moreover, populist governments significantly underperformed – in terms of GDP and macroeconomic stability – their nonpopulist counterfactuals (Funke et al., 2020). Bellodi et al. (2022) capture similar dynamics also at the local level, showing that populist mayors lead to lower efficiency in municipal government performance and tend to deteriorate financial sustainability. It is therefore interesting to investigate the determinants and dynamics driving the success of political actors.

The literature that examines the drivers and dynamics of extreme voting proposed two conflicting theories: *the economic insecurity perspective* and *the cultural backlash perspective*. The former predicts a stronger support for extremist parties among those individuals employed in sectors that have lost from recent structural transformations of western economies, such as the expansion of global markets and technological advances. The cultural backlash perspective considers the consensus of extremist, populist parties as a reaction of the electorate which feels threatened by the erosion of traditional values and the progressive value change (Norries and Inglehart, 2016). While the literature provided evidence supporting both views, there is still no consensus on the interaction between economic and cultural factors.

The present policy brief investigates the relevance of different economic and non-economic factors in explaining the rise of extremist parties, also exploring possible interactions between these dimensions.

2. Setting and empirical analysis

We aim at investigating whether the recent rise of extremist parties in most western countries can be explained by economic and/or non-economic factors, while also considering possible mutually reinforcing dynamics which may arise from the interactions between economic and cultural dimensions. Belgium, and especially its Flemish region, provides an interesting opportunity to examine the dynamics driving the electoral performance of extremist parties, in particular those characterised by a nationalistic rhetoric and/or right-wing populist traits. The Flemish region of Belgium is, indeed, characterised by a long-standing tradition of nationalistic, populist, right-wing parties which have displayed volatile electoral performances. Although presenting these peculiarities, this region has experienced some political trends common to many other established democracies - particularly in the European context - such as a recent rise of extremist political actors and a plummeting voter turnout (IDEA, 2016). For these reasons, the Flemish region of Belgium offers a great opportunity for research on these issues, possibly providing insights also relevant for contexts characterised by a democratic political setting affected by analogous trends.

The analysis builds on a unique panel dataset comprising registry data – about demography, crime, income, poverty, unemployment and migration – covering 300 Flemish municipalities in Belgium, and electoral results at the canton level for Belgian national elections between 1999 and 2019.

We employ a canton-level fixed effects regression model – also including a time trend – to estimate our parameters, in order to capture the unobserved heterogeneity across cantons and any other canton-specific factor which may influence the electoral dynamic. Furthermore, a particular focus is devoted to the analysis of the relationship between migration dynamics, economic and cultural factors and right-wing populist electoral performance. The outcome of interest for this empirical analysis is parties' vote share, where different parties have been aggregated into four broad political families which allow better comparability with similar political contexts abroad: left, green, centre, right.

3. Results

Our empirical findings suggest that different dynamics may lay behind the electoral performances of extreme left and green parties on the one hand, and right-wing, populist on the other.

Looking at the economic factors, a positive correlation arises between populist right's vote share and an improving economic outlook. This contrasts the common intuition that economic distress correlates with populist right votes. In particular, an increase in unemployment correlates with a weaker electoral performance of the populist right. Electoral success of extreme left and green political families is instead correlated with worsening economic outcomes.

More in detail, three economic factors – unemployment, income and child poverty - seem to have a consistent influence on the vote shares obtained by left and green political families: while higher unemployment and child poverty are associated with higher vote shares, the

opposite occurs for income. The latter results are in line with the traditional role of extreme left parties in representing those groups in the population that experience economic difficulties. On the other extreme, the performance of right-wing populist can hardly be explained relying on the economic insecurity perspective, as it does not seem that worsening economic outcomes trigger their support. Furthermore, we find that the electoral success of right-wing populists is linked to smaller cantons and those with older electorates.

The findings regarding immigration – considered as a factor unveiling the cultural dimension in voters' behaviour – show that immigration inflows do not influence left and green parties' vote shares, while they are strongly correlated with right-wing, populist electoral success. Immigration inflows have a positive influence on right-wing vote share, regardless of the country of origin. The interactions between economic and immigration variables are hardly significant, signaling that economic distress does not act as a trigger or amplifier of right-wing, populist electoral success in the presence of migration inflows. This outcome provides evidence against the “culture-time-economics” perspective – according to which dire economic conditions serve as a trigger for cultural factors to emerge – while supporting the “culture-plus-economics” one, assigning prominence to cultural elements (Guriev and Papaioannou, 2022). Furthermore, the influence of immigration on electoral consensus for right-wing parties is stronger in more homogenous communities, where group identification and communal values are more salient (Alesina and Tabellini, 2022).

Our results hold even when migration inflow is instrumented, lending support to

a possible causal interpretation based on the group threat theory. According to this perspective, intergroup competition over resources leads ingroup – i.e. natives – to develop more negative attitudes towards the outgroup – i.e. immigrants, perceived as a threat – the larger the size of the latter.

All the above findings, capturing a significant electoral response to immigration, seem to reveal anti-cosmopolitan and nativist sentiments that underlie the cultural backlash perspective.

4. Policy recommendations

Our results have relevant policy implications as it is a political responsibility to make sure that migration flows smoothly without being perceived as a threat neither in economic nor in cultural terms. For this reason, immigration policies should take into consideration both the economic and the cultural dimensions.

Regarding the economic dimension, policy makers should tackle natives' feeling of threat driven by the identification of immigrants as source of additional competition over finite public resources. In this respect, information campaigns might be a useful tool to reassure people about their social rights and entitlements. First, they should clarify the actual effect of migration inflows on social programs already in place. Second, they should underline the active role played by newcomers – on average younger than native population – in making welfare state economically more sustainable, through their social security contributions, for western rapidly aging populations.

Integrating the cultural dimension makes appropriate policy design more

challenging. Our findings highlight that the effect of immigration on right-wing vote share is stronger in more homogeneous communities, thus suggesting that higher frequency of intergroup (natives and immigrant groups) contacts is conducive to more positive attitudes between groups – as predicted by the contact hypothesis (Allport, 1954). On this basis, policy-makers should design policies that ensure gradual and moderate inflows, which are geographically spread across urban and rural areas, in order to encourage smooth intergroup contacts and thus mitigate intergroup hostility.

Moreover, literature shows that every wave of immigration triggers hostility towards the newcomers, while possibly reclassifying immigrants from previous waves as member of the majority group (Alesina and Tabellini, 2022). This suggests that the mere fact of being a new immigrant – i.e. a member of the outgroup – is a crucial factor in triggering hostility, even when compared to other factors, such as specific group identification dimensions (such as race or religion) which can instead change over time. This dynamic is corroborated by our results showing that immigration is a very relevant explanatory factor for populist right electoral success regardless of immigrants' country of origin. These findings call for policies which tackle more broadly the cultural dimension – possibly involving also the younger part of the population – and aim at preventing the ex-ante formation of judgements, or prejudice, about newcomers.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

Inglehart, R. F. & Norris, P. (2016). Trump, Brexit, and the Rise of Populism: Economic Have-Nots and Cultural Backlash. HKS Working Paper No. RWP16-026.

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Further Information:

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